

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62532 Max: 62443	1477 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 2184-87 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *deposit along threshold*
 Covered by SU: 1384 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL MATRIX
☐ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☒ Tufo (specify) F ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive Compaction ☐ Hard ☒ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☒ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit	☐ Original ☒ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	Depth: ☒ Original ☐ Not Original
Southern Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	☐ Original ☒ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1414, 1394, 1504
Is covered by: 1384	Covers: 1410
Is cut by: 1229	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *dry, sunny conditions* *SU is still in situ it has not been excavated*

DESCRIPTION: Position within sector: *western part of Trench B 204; just beyond threshold of house*
 Shape: *long rectangular*

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): *Slope Down to south (to entrance)*
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) Medium (range) Large (range) Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify) Crushed tufo

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: approx. 2 meters x 1m

Description: Crushed, Fired tufo
Floor/Floor preparation preserved
in small area at threshold
of house. Tiles & amphora
fragments remain in the
northern corner.

INTERPRETATION

Floor surface made of compacted, crushed, fired tufo
fragments. Probably the earliest floor of the building.
It is at least the earliest floor surface we found
traces of.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	<u>CHM, JARR</u>	on	<u>1.8.2009, 3.8.11</u>
Revised by	<u>CHM, CHM</u>	on	<u>3.8.2009, 25.6.2012</u>
PDFd by	<u>ELC</u>	on	<u>3.8.2011</u>
Entered by		on	